

Arsenic Crisis in Bangladesh: A Looming Threat to Public Health

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Abstract:

According to an assessment by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2012, the pervasive arsenic epidemic in Bangladesh has become a grave threat to public health, taking an estimated 43,000 lives per year. In Bangladesh, millions of people are potentially exposed to health risks since arsenic pollution is common in soil and groundwater as a result of natural processes. This article explores the complex problem of arsenic pollution, explaining its characteristics, its sources, and the terrible effects it has on individuals who are exposed. The study emphasizes the sneaky character of arsenic-related disorders, the difficulties in treating them, and the socioeconomic effects on people, families, and society at large. The essay underlines the necessity of tackling this situation immediately to respect the principles of sustainable development and ensure everyone has access to clean water and a healthier future. It does this by concluding historical and modern research.

Keywords:

arsenic contamination, public health, water crisis, Bangladesh, arsenicosis, sustainable development, water pollution, groundwater, health hazards, arsenic-related illnesses

Introduction:

A severe catastrophe affecting millions of lives has resulted from the pernicious danger of arsenic pollution in Bangladesh, which has cast a lengthy shadow over the country's public health landscape. A naturally occurring mineral and natural substance called arsenic has emerged as a stealthy and fearsome foe, contaminating the very water sources that people depend on. This article looks into the intricate web of the arsenic epidemic, revealing its causes, manifestations, and significant ramifications for societal well-being and public health.

The discovery of arsenic in groundwater in certain areas of Bangladesh as early as 1993 signalled the beginning of a protracted health emergency. This disaster has gotten worse over time, with frighteningly high amounts of arsenic contamination being identified in numerous locations, making it one of the most serious environmental health issues the country is currently facing. Arsenicosis, a condition brought on by continuous exposure to arsenic-contaminated water, hurts the health and well-being of persons who are affected.

By exploring the chemical element of arsenic, its sources, and the methods by which it contaminates the water supply, this article aims to provide insight into the complex nature of the arsenic situation in Bangladesh. We seek to place the size of the dilemma facing Bangladesh in context by looking at the historical trajectory of arsenic poisoning both locally and globally. This

study also explores the physical and social effects of arsenicosis, illuminating their wide-ranging and frequently disastrous effects on people and communities.

The complex interplay between water scarcity, contamination, and public health underscores the urgency of addressing this crisis through collaborative and holistic approaches. As the United Nations strives to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals, the arsenic crisis stands as an impediment to the fundamental right to clean water and adequate sanitation. Through rigorous scientific inquiry, informed policymaking, and community-driven initiatives, it is our collective responsibility to chart a course toward mitigating the arsenic crisis and safeguarding the well-being of Bangladesh's population.

In the subsequent sections, we will delve into the various dimensions of the arsenic crisis, from its chemical properties to its devastating health consequences, shedding light on the imperative need for swift and comprehensive action.

Discussion:

In Bangladesh, arsenic contamination claims the lives of at least 43,000 people annually, according to a 2012 World Health Organization report. A survey released in 2016 by the New York-based human rights organization Human Rights Watch (HRW) estimated that 20 million individuals in Bangladesh were exposed to arsenic at some point throughout their lifetime. Arsenic is a mineral substance that occurs in nature, as those who have studied chemistry in class 9–10 or earlier when they have read general science books in various courses are aware. No taste or smell exists for arsenic. It has an atomic mass of 74.9 and an atomic number of 33. Once more, why is arsenic being discussed? Why is arsenic harmful to the general people? Why is Bangladesh facing an arsenic crisis? To get answers to these questions, we need to know a little more about arsenic and arsenic contamination.

Arsenic is an elementary substance, as was previously established. Arsenic can take on various forms. But the only arsenic that is metallic is grey. In the industrial world, only this form is important because it is mostly used to make different kinds of semiconductors. When arsenic is present as an elementary material in nature, it is non-toxic and does not dissolve in water. However, when it forms oxides in the air, it turns poisonous. The most significant source of arsenic is soil, though it can be found in other places as well. A layer of rock containing Pyrites is found beneath the soil. This chemical substance contains arsenic. When we get water from the ground using tube wells or other methods, arsenic may be present in the water. Since arsenic is dissolved in water, it is invisible to the eye. The issue is whether consuming water with arsenic dissolved is hazardous to health. Here, it is important to realize that arsenic is a mineral element. Water always contains trace amounts of arsenic, but when these levels rise above the safe range, the body is put at risk. A litre of water is considered to be polluted by the World Health Organization if it has 10 micrograms of arsenic in it. But by Bangladeshi regulations, water is considered contaminated if it has 50 micrograms of arsenic per litre. The WHO standard is currently regarded as more acceptable. Arsenicosis is a condition that can develop in people who drink water that contains arsenic. Arsenicosis is one of the biggest hazards to public health in Bangladesh because there is no effective therapy for it. Arsenic-related illnesses are more likely to develop if people consume arsenic-containing food and drink or cook with it.

Arsenic pollution has been a problem in many nations worldwide since the beginning of the 20th century when the first arsenic issue was identified in Taiwan. Numerous Asian nations, Latin American nations, and even in the USA groundwater have all experienced arsenic pollution. Argentina was where arsenic studies initially began in 1938. In addition to Argentina, more than 50 other nations, including Mexico, Chile, the United States, Taiwan, China, India, and Bangladesh, are all struggling with arsenic poisoning. There are about 20 known instances of arsenic pollution in groundwater worldwide. Asia was home to four of these major cases.

The excessive amounts of arsenic in Bangladesh's drinking water are referred to as the country's "Arsenic Problem." By conducting tests in many tube wells, the Directorate of Public Health and Engineering of Bangladesh discovered the presence of arsenic in the groundwater in Baragharia Mauza of Sadar Upazila of Chapainawabganj district in 1993. The National Institute for Preventive and Social Medicine (NIPSOM), the Ground Water Circle of the Bangladesh Water Development Board (BWDB), the Geological Survey of Bangladesh (GSB), the Bangladesh Atomic Energy Commission, and other government agencies began looking for signs of arsenic contamination in the nation later.

After that, in 2001, the British Geological Survey analyzed the water from tube wells in 61 districts of Bangladesh and discovered that 42% of the water surpassed WHO standards and that 25% of the water contained arsenic, which is getting more and more commonplace every day. Except for Cox's Bazar, Rangamati, Khagrachari, Bandarban, and Sherpur, 59 of Bangladesh's 64 districts had arsenic contamination. 11.8% of the population of Bangladesh drank arsenic water in 2019, with 40% of those people living in Sylhet and 31% in Chattagram, according to data from the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS). When arsenic levels in the whole country's tube wells were checked in 2003, the Directorate of Public Health Engineering reported that high levels of arsenic were discovered in 29% of the water. Twenty years passed there is no other survey is held after that. A study on the water testing of tube wells in 54 Bangladeshi districts was released by the Bangladeshi government and UNICEF on March 22, 2010. This provides information on the 31,497 villages, 2,000 unions, 233 Upazilas, and 47 Districts that are affected by arsenic pollution. According to Bangladeshi guidelines, locations are considered arsenic-contaminated if tube well water contains 5% arsenic or more. The Directorate of Public Health and Engineering launched the "Arsenic Risk Mitigation in Water Supply" initiative in 2019. From mid-2021 to September 2022, 3,200 union tube wells across the nation were examined as part of the study. A total of 54 lacks had 30 thousand 880 tube wells examined, and of those, 7 lacks had 55 thousand 548, or 13.91%, more arsenic than was allowed.

As mentioned earlier, those who get arsenic poisoning due to drinking arsenic-contaminated water are called 'Arsenicosis' patients. Prolonged use of water containing small amounts of arsenic can cause serious damage to health. It takes several years to fully spread throughout the body. Fever, vomiting, headache, unusual body aches, blood dysentery and diarrhoea have been identified as symptoms of this disease. In the initial stage, black spots appear on the affected patient or the skin color turns black. The skin, palms of the hands and feet become hard and crusty and may appear as small hard bumps that gradually turn black. Later, white, red or black spots appear in various places on the skin. The hands and feet swell and the palms and soles crack and hard calluses form. Eventually the kidneys, liver, and lungs become enlarged and tumorous. A research paper

published in 2010 found that drinking water containing arsenic increases the risk of death. The risk of death also depends on how much arsenic is in the water and how long a person has been drinking it. Although arsenic poisoning is not the main cause of death, it increases the risk of death. There is a relationship between daily total arsenic intake and urinary arsenic concentrations. If arsenic is high in water, the risk of death is also high. Studies have shown that drinking arsenic-contaminated water increases the average risk of death from common diseases by 21% and the risk of death from chronic diseases by 24%. Arsenic poisoning in people drinking arsenic-contaminated water can cause liver, skin, kidney, lung and heart cancer. Due to arsenic, various diseases have already occurred in the hands and feet of various people. Many even have to amputate their fingers and toes to prevent the spread of the disease.

The number of people impacted by arsenic poisoning and their medical conditions are not currently known by the Department of Health in any great depth. Beginning in 2023, Health Minister Zahid Malek stated that there are currently over 65 thousand 910 persons in the nation who have arsenic sickness during a question-and-answer session in the National Parliament. The most recent Khana inspection report (2012) served as the basis for the preparation of this material. Data from the 2019 cluster survey conducted by UNICEF and the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics show that 11.8% of the population in the nation drinks water that has been poisoned with arsenic. A little over 2 crore people use arsenic-contaminated water. There were 38 thousand 412 patients with arsenic contamination nationwide in 2003. According to a survey done by the Department of Health's various institutions, there would be 57,280 people with arsenic in 2023. Eight thousand patients are arsenic-infected in the first three months of this year. This figure is far higher. In Bangladesh, arsenic poisoning claims the lives of at least 43,000 people annually, according to a World Health Organization estimate from 2012.

The shallow tube well water in the nation was clean even 30 years ago, but arsenic has slowly gotten into it. Experts claim that there is no cure for arsenic poisoning. Arsenic poisoning can currently be treated most successfully through preventative measures. Numerous reports indicate that each year, doctors identify people with arsenic poisoning, and more than half of them pass away. The hazard to the public's health practically exists here. Because, firstly, paying for an arsenic patient's medical costs over time puts additional strain on his family and impedes both their socioeconomic progress and that of society as a whole. Secondly, a person who suffers from arsenic-related illnesses for a prolonged period of time loses his or her ability to function normally and is unable to contribute to the social advancement of himself, his or her family, or society. Thirdly, although though arsenic-related illnesses are not contagious, neighbours or family members do not frequently interact with patients who are impacted by the poison or their families, which is bad for the patient's mental health.

Arsenic-related medical costs and monetary losses to families and society have not been extensively explored or documented. However, it goes without saying that arsenic poisoning prevents locals from having access to safe water, which is a basic need. Instead, it is because it is affecting their quality of life that it is being referred to as a looming threat to public health. After all, the sixth Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) of the United Nations is access to clean water and adequate sanitation. The SDGs cannot be achieved without everyone having access to a clean water system that is community-focused, sustainable, and ecologically friendly. However, arsenic

poisoning has brought about a significant problem in Bangladesh's ability to ensure that everyone has access to clean water, which poses a substantial risk to the nation's public health.

Conclusion:

As a result, the arsenic problem in Bangladesh poses a serious and impending risk to the public's health and demands prompt attention and coordinated action. The overwhelming number of lives lost each year and the widespread effects on countless people highlight how urgent it is to address this problem. Water sources have become contaminated with arsenic due to natural sources, causing widespread arsenicosis and other health problems. The lack of a permanent treatment emphasizes prevention as the key strategy, emphasizing the need for long-lasting and community-focused solutions.

Arsenic poisoning has repercussions that extend beyond the victim and have an impact on families, communities, and society as a whole. The burden of medical expenses slowed socioeconomic development, and decreased quality of life for individuals affected are significant issues that necessitate thorough management. The situation also hinders Bangladesh's efforts to meet the Sustainable Development Goals of the UN, particularly in terms of ensuring access to clean water and sufficient sanitary facilities.

Governmental institutions, international organizations, researchers, and local communities must work together to address this epidemic successfully. A thorough response must include effective methods for locating and reducing arsenic pollution in water sources as well as focused medical therapies. Campaigns for public awareness and community involvement can encourage people to take charge of their health.

Taking on the arsenic problem in Bangladesh involves a multifaceted strategy that incorporates academic investigation, legislative action, and community action. By taking these steps, the country can pave the path for a healthier future in which everyone has access to clean and safe water, reducing the serious risks posed by arsenic contamination and guaranteeing a sustainable and vibrant society.

Reference:

1. Ahmad SA, Khan MH, Haque M. Arsenic contamination in groundwater in Bangladesh: implications and challenges for healthcare policy. *Risk Manag Health Policy*. 2018 Nov 30; 11:251-261. doi: 10.2147/RMHP.S153188. PMID: 30584381; PMCID: PMC6281155.
2. BD, D. (1998). *MYcÖ RvZšç x evsjv ž`k miKvi*. [online] Available at: https://dphe.portal.gov.bd/sites/default/files/files/dphe.portal.gov.bd/page/7e716d34_58de_494a_aaa3_105f03c3c101/Arsenic%20mitigation%20Manual.pdf [Accessed 9 Aug. 2023].
3. Islam, M.S. and Islam, F. (2013). *Arsenic Contamination in Groundwater in Bangladesh: An Environmental And Social Disaster | IWA Publishing*. [online] Iwapublishing.com. Available at: <https://www.iwapublishing.com/news/arsenic-contamination-groundwater-bangladesh-environmental-and-social-disaster>.

4. Online, D.S. (2023). *The number of arsenic patients in the country is 65 thousand 910: Health Minister*. [online] The Daily Star Bangla. Available at: <https://bangla.thedailystar.net/health/disease/news-447801> [Accessed 9 Aug. 2023].
5. Prothom Alo (2016). *Information from HRW 2 crore people in Bangladesh are victims of arsenic pollution*. [online] www.prothomalo.com. Available at: <https://www.prothomalo.com/bangladesh/>.
6. Rahman, Md.A. (2021). *Arsenic pollution and prevention in Bangladesh*. [online] www.protidinersangbad.com. Available at: <https://www.protidinersangbad.com/>.
7. Rahman, S. (2022). *14% of tub wells in the country have excessive arsenic*. [online] Prothomalo. Available at: <https://www.prothomalo.com/bangladesh/it46v4u3k4> [Accessed 9 Aug. 2023].
8. Unicef (2018). *ARSENIC PRIMER Guidance on the Investigation & Mitigation of Arsenic Contamination*. [online] Available at: <https://www.unicef.org/media/91296/file/UNICEF-WHO-Arsenic-Primer.pdf>.
9. Yachmin, G.S. (2012). *Arsenic Contamination: Context Bangladesh*. [online] www.dainiksangbadpratidin.com. Available at: <https://www.dainiksangbadpratidin.com/details.php?id=74080> [Accessed 9 Aug. 2023].